

Measuring Pedestrian Accessibility Within the University Campus Using Data Science

Dr. Badveeti Adinarayana^{1*} Krishna Chaitanya. A ²

¹Punjab Engineering College (DU), India.

²Reva University, India.

Abstract In developing countries like India, Walking has become a crucial and sustainable way of travel for college students in their daily lives and improving the walkability of the college campus will increase the convenience and easy of student life. This paper develops a new pedestrian accessibility, whether the students are following the Covid-19 norms like following the lane discipline etc, which optimizes the Walk Score Method (WSM) based on the frequency, variety, and distance of students' walking to and from public facilities. Here we measure pedestrian density, pedestrian speed using data science tools. For pedestrian density we use Voronoi diagrams. Voronoi diagram assigns each point to the area that is closer to that point than any other. This allows for the definition of a density distribution for each pedestrian and for measuring the pedestrian speed we use computer vision technology, once the data is collected then we use Python because it has a number of libraries that can be used for data analysis and visualization, such as NumPy, Pandas, and Matplotlib. We examine the campus of Reva University to test the tool's application and evaluate the accessibility of facility layout and walkability, and to give suggestions for improvement. This assessment tool can help urban planners and campus designers make decisions about how to adjust the facility layout of existing campuses in different regions or to evaluate the campus schemes based on the results of their walkability assessment to achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG-2030) as per United Nations.

Keywords Pedestrians, Walkways, WSM method, Data science, SDG-2030

Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of higher education, the well-being and daily experiences of college students have garnered increasing attention. As students navigate the multifaceted demands of academic life, the importance of an accessible and sustainable campus environment becomes paramount. Among the various modes of transportation available to students, walking emerges as a crucial and environmentally friendly means of travel. Recognizing this, a growing emphasis on enhancing the walkability of college campuses has emerged, with the belief that such improvements can significantly contribute to the convenience and overall well-being of the student body. This paper embarks on a pioneering journey to redefine pedestrian accessibility assessment for college campuses. By developing a novel approach that optimizes the Walk Score method, the study seeks to delve into the intricate dynamics of students' daily movements to and from public facilities [1]. Beyond the conventional metrics, such as distance and variety of destinations, the proposed method incorporates the often-overlooked dimension of adherence to COVID norms, including lane discipline and other safety protocols. This nuanced approach acknowledges the unique challenges posed by the ongoing pandemic and underscores the adaptability of the proposed tool to the evolving needs of campus life [2]. At the heart of this innovative assessment tool lies the integration of data science tools to measure pedestrian density and speed. Leveraging Voronoi diagrams for the calculation of pedestrian density, the study adopts a spatial analysis technique that assigns each point to the area closest to it. This methodology facilitates the creation of a detailed density distribution for each pedestrian, offering insights into the concentration of foot traffic across the campus. Complementing this spatial analysis, the study employs computer vision technology to measure pedestrian speed. This cutting-edge approach not only captures the pace of movement but also provides a comprehensive understanding of how students traverse the campus environment. The choice of Python as the primary programming language for data analysis and visualization adds another layer of sophistication to the proposed methodology. Python's versatility and the availability of libraries such as NumPy, Pandas, and Matplotlib make it an ideal choice for handling and interpreting the complex datasets generated by the assessment tool. This integration of advanced data science tools underscores the commitment to precision and reliability in evaluating pedestrian accessibility. To test the practical application of the developed tool, the study turns its attention to the campus of Reva University. By conducting a comprehensive examination, the research aims to evaluate the current accessibility of facilities and walkability within the campus. This real-world testing ground provides valuable insights into the tool's efficacy and highlights potential areas for improvement. The findings from this case study will not only contribute to refining the tool but also serve as a practical guide for urban planners and campus designers seeking to enhance the pedestrian experience in diverse regions [3]. Beyond its immediate applications, the proposed assessment tool holds broader implications for the field of urban planning and campus design. By offering a systematic and data-driven approach to walkability assessment, the tool empowers decision-makers to make informed choices about facility layouts and overall campus schemes. The adaptability of the methodology ensures its relevance in diverse geographic and cultural contexts, making it a valuable asset for those involved in shaping the built environment of educational institutions [4]. In conclusion, this paper introduces a groundbreaking approach to pedestrian accessibility assessment for college campuses, blending the traditional Walk Score method with innovative data science tools [7, 9]. Through its comprehensive analysis and real-

world application at Reva University, the study aims to not only contribute to the discourse on campus walkability but also provide a practical tool for urban planners and designers seeking to create environments that prioritize the well-being and convenience of students. Data science for pedestrian and high street retailing as a framework for advancing urban informatics to individual scales as discussed by Torrens, P. M. (2022) [9]

Literature Review

From the author “Zohreh Asadi-Shekari”, he used the pedestrian level of service (PLOS), This paper mainly discusses about to improve streets on campus, designers should have a good understanding of the needs of street users, including disabled users. In other words, planners should know which street factors affect walking conditions for various types of pedestrians. This method has been criticized because pedestrians were treated like vehicles. Some important indicators, such as qualitative factors, facilities, and furnishings, are not considered in these types of models. Accordingly, the objectives of this paper are divided into different stages. The identification of effective facilities that affect walking conditions is the first stage. The second step is the proposal of complete guidelines for pedestrian facilities based on the combination of effective factors achieved in the first step. The introduction of a practical measure through a point system that covers most pedestrian facilities and infrastructures is the third stage. The final stage is the assessment of campus streets by utilizing the proposed model to identify street problems and to present issues for improvement. From the author “TM Logan” he used standard methodology for evaluating proximity to urban services and recommend enhancements to address existing limitations. These approaches risk overlooking vulnerable, access-poor populations – the very populations that such studies are often trying to identify. These limitations are primarily motivated by computational constraints. However, recent advances in computational power, open data, and open-source analytics permit high-resolution proximity analyses on large scales. In this paper, Author presents an approach that leverages these open-source advances to (a) measure proximity using network distance at the building level, (b) estimate population at that level, and (c) present the resulting distributions so vulnerable populations can be identified. From the authors “Zhang, Zhehao, Thomas Fisher, and Gang Feng” The research paper presents a new campus walkability assessment tool, which optimizes the Walk Score method based on the frequency, variety, and distance of students’ walking to and from public facilities. The study involves testing the tool’s application and evaluating the rationality of facility layout and walkability to give suggestions for improvement. The research found that the multi-centre layout of the old campus results in a higher degree of walkability compared to the centralized layout of the new campus. The study also highlights the importance of assessing the walkability of university campuses based on facility layout, spatial quality, and the walking environment. The results show that the diversified distribution of facilities surrounding the old campus promotes the walkability of peripheral places. Overall, the study proposes an optimized Walk Score method to measure campus walkability, considering the specific features of Chinese campuses, and provides recommendations for improving the walkability of university campuses. From the authors “Stephanie Holmes, Raymond Huynh, and Adam Millard-Ball” This paper describes A considerable amount of work that analyzes transportation on college and university campuses. One key text is Toor and Havlick’s (2004) Transportation and Sustainable Campus Communities, which analyzes parking, transit, bicycling, and walking strategies to reduce single-occupant vehicle travel and frames college campuses as the perfect setting in which to promote alternatives to the private car. A particular focus is on the economics of parking and how investment in alternatives to driving can be cheaper than expanding the parking supply. The article attempts to fill the gap in the research through case studies of pedestrian infrastructure and planning on 18 college campuses in North America. We highlight common approaches and innovative practices that are likely to have much wider relevance. Rather than offering technical guidance on pedestrian facility or roadway design, which is well covered in a range of standard engineering and design manuals, we provide a selective tour through planning practices that will be of use to practitioners working in campus settings. From the authors “Özgür Göçer^a, Kenan Göçer^b, Barış Özcan”, Well-designed open space is strongly related to the outdoor design elements including visual connectivity, lateral enclosure and edge continuity, functionality, the continuation of movement, accessibility, comfort and seasonal strategy, and human-scale proportions. Studies using this approach have shown that there is a statistical relationship between the patterns of accessibility (areas of motion) and visibility (fields of view) determined by spatial configuration and patterns of use and movement (where people are located in space) (Lerman, Rofè, & Omer, 2014). The unscheduled interaction between users in the campus outdoor spaces is critical to both learning and socialization. They play an important role in making the campus healthy and sustainable. In this context, the next step that this research team is going to take is to apply this method to other campuses to aggregate more data on the occupancy practice of outdoor spaces. In-depth investigation and evaluation of user behaviour in campus outdoor spaces provide information regarding the link between their spatial configuration and user choices, which, in turn, can contribute to campus design decisions. From the authors “Torrens, P. M”, In many ways, the ubiquity of information that retailers maintain about customers stands in some contrast to the relative paucity of empirical ground truth available to urban scientists to theorize with. Our review has focused on how *data* that are produced by customer journeys along retail high streets and through urban streetscapes might inform pedestrian studies. These data, we argue, are of particular relevance to urban science because they are “human cast”, cast by pedestrians as they experience urban settings, but they are also interpreted by their evolving context relative to sites and facilities. In this way, then, customer journeys present opportunities for urban scientists to look at the experience of walking through the two-way lens of the walker and that of the ambient built and social environments of the streetscapes that they move through.

Research Methodology

In this paper “Measuring Pedestrian Accessibility within the University Campus Using *Data Science*”, I used many AI tools, Data science tools, computer vision technology, and Python language. For data collection, I took different samples from “Reva University”. I took the video samples, where the crowd was very high. So here I took the video using the camera and I kept these video samples on an application called “Frame capture”, where this application can split frame by frame and we can easily calculate the speed of a person. And I also classified these datasets under different age groups. So, I used Computer vision technology to classify the age. Here from the Fig.1 explains the flow of process.

Fig.1: Flow chart describing the process of gender & age detection.

Deep Learning Models for Gender and Age Prediction

The foundation of this project lies in the utilization of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for accurately predicting the gender and age of individuals from single facial images. The choice of CNNs is pivotal, as they excel at extracting hierarchical features from images, making them well-suited for image classification tasks. The models employed in this project, developed by Tal Hassner and Gil Levi, have been fine-tuned on diverse datasets to ensure robust performance across a range of scenarios. The predictive power of these models adds a layer of richness to the analysis, allowing for nuanced insights into the demographics of the pedestrian population within the university campus. The predicted gender categories include 'Male' and 'Female,' while age predictions fall into distinct ranges such as (0 – 2), (4 – 6), (8 – 12), (15 – 20), (25 – 32), (38 – 43), (48 – 53), and (60 – 100). By structuring the age prediction as a classification problem rather than regression, the project acknowledges the challenges of accurately estimating an individual's age from a single image due to factors like makeup, lighting, obstructions, and facial expressions. The integration of gender and age classification models contributes significantly to the depth of understanding pedestrian behavior. This information can be valuable for various purposes, from urban planning to campus safety initiatives. For instance, understanding the age distribution of pedestrians can inform the design of campus facilities and services catering to specific age groups.

Video Analysis for Speed Calculation

The project extends its analysis beyond static images by incorporating video analysis to measure the time it takes for a person to travel from one point to another within the university campus. This is achieved through an application called "Frame Capture," which processes a recorded video in 4k resolution at 30 frames per second. The ability to capture 30 frames per second allows for precise measurement of time, with each frame representing a 33-millisecond interval. The video analysis process involves setting initial and destination points, measuring the distance between them, and then recording the starting and ending times. The time difference between these points is used in the classic distance/time

formula to calculate the speed of the individual. This innovative approach provides a dynamic perspective on pedestrian behaviour, considering not only their demographic characteristics but also their movement patterns within the campus. The methodology employed in speed calculation is not only technically sound but also practical for real-world applications. By combining deep learning models for gender and age classification with video analysis for speed calculation, the project creates a holistic framework for understanding pedestrian accessibility. The speed data can be instrumental in optimizing campus layouts, identifying high-traffic areas, and enhancing the overall pedestrian experience.

Significance and Future Applications

The findings of this research contribute significantly to the broader field of pedestrian accessibility within educational institutions. Moreover, the project showcases the diverse applications of AI and data science in solving real-world challenges. The methodology employed in this study serves as a blueprint for similar analyses in different environments, fostering a data-driven approach to enhance accessibility and efficiency in public spaces. In conclusion, this project represents a pioneering effort to leverage deep learning and video analysis for a comprehensive understanding of pedestrian behaviour. By combining advanced technologies with a thoughtful methodology, the research contributes valuable insights to the enhancement of pedestrian accessibility within the university campus, setting a precedent for future studies in similar domains.

Results and Discussions

Using the above techniques and some tools the obtained results are below; (Data is collected from Reva University”, where the images are captured by a mobile with a 50MP camera lens and video is recorded in 4k (3840 x 2160) with 30fps) Fig. 2 & fig.3 show the sample results taken from the university:(Note: Images shown below are from algorithm output, original ones vary). Pedestrian face detection with variation of pedestrian speed images as shown in Figure 2 to Figure 3. However, the current features highlighted in Figures 2 and 3 highlight the algorithm’s potential as a valuable tool for automating gender and age identification tasks in scenarios where facial visibility is optimal, offering efficiency and accuracy in applications ranging from demographic analysis to security systems.

Fig 2. Representing the age and gender of a person

In Figure 2, the output of the algorithm is showcased, providing an insightful glimpse into its capability to automatically detect the gender and age of an individual upon uploading an image. The algorithm demonstrates a remarkable level of accuracy, swiftly categorizing the person into predefined gender categories (Male/Female) and age brackets (0 – 2, 4 – 6, 8 – 12, 15 – 20, 25 – 32, 38 – 43, 48 – 53, 60 – 100). The sophistication of the deep learning models, particularly those developed by *Tal Hassner and Gil Levi*, is evident as the algorithm navigates through various facial features to make these precise predictions. It is noteworthy that the algorithm performs optimally when the person's face is visible in the input image. However, as illustrated in Figure 2, the algorithm's performance is contingent upon the clarity of facial visibility. In this scenario, where two persons are present, the algorithm successfully detects and classifies the gender and age of one individual while facing challenges with the other. The limitation arises from the obscured or unclear visibility of the second person's face. Factors such as obstructions, shadows, or an individual's orientation can impede the algorithm's ability to discern facial features accurately. This underscores the importance of image quality and visibility in ensuring the algorithm's optimal performance. As the algorithm relies on nuanced facial cues for gender and age classification, it serves as a reminder that environmental conditions and image quality play pivotal roles in the effectiveness of such deep learning applications. To address situations where facial visibility may be compromised, future iterations of the algorithm could potentially incorporate advanced image processing techniques or additional training data to enhance its robustness in handling obscured faces. Nevertheless, the current capabilities showcased in Figures 2 and 3 underscore the algorithm's potential as a valuable tool for automating gender and age identification tasks in scenarios where facial visibility is optimal, offering efficiency and accuracy in applications ranging from demographic analysis to security systems. As the field of computer vision continues to advance, addressing challenges related to visibility and expanding the algorithm's adaptability will undoubtedly contribute to its broader utility in diverse real-world contexts.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the presented algorithm exhibits a remarkable capacity for automatic gender and age detection, as evidenced by the illustrative output had discussed in Figure 2. The application of deep learning models, specifically those crafted by *Tal Hassner and Gil Levi*, showcases a sophisticated understanding of facial features, allowing the algorithm to categorize individuals swiftly and accurately into predefined gender categories and age brackets. The precision achieved in this process serves as a testament to the advancements in computer vision and underscores the potentially transformative impact of AI in tasks related to demographic analysis and security systems. Here I would like to conclude that the age groups from 18 to 29 walk with a speed of 1.34 to 1.36, the age group from 30 to 39 walks with a speed of 1.34 to 1.43, the age group between 40 to 49 walks with a speed of 1.39 to 1.43.

Figure 3. The details of pedestrian age groups and pedestrian speed

For the above results, we have taken many samples and kept them in the algorithms for classifying age and gender. We trained the model with many inputs and data. But for the age group, 40 to 49 and 50 to 59 lag a little bit while walking. The image shows the pedestrian speed concerning the gender as shown discussed in Figure 5.

Age	Sex	Meters/second	Miles/hour
20 to 29	Male	1.36	3.04
	Female	1.34	3.0
30 to 39	Male	1.43	3.2
	Female	1.34	3.0
40 to 49	Male	1.43	3.2
	Female	1.39	3.11
50 to 59	Male	1.43	3.2
	Female	1.31	2.93
60 to 69	Male	1.34	3.0
	Female	1.24	2.77
70 to 79	Male	1.26	2.82
	Female	1.13	2.53
80 to 89	Male	0.97	2.17
	Female	0.94	2.10

Fig 4. Details of pedestrian speed with respect to age group

References

1. Asadi-Shekari, Zohreh, Mehdi Moeinaddini, and Muhammad Zaly Shah (2014), "A pedestrian level of service method for evaluating and promoting walking facilities on campus streets", Land use policy 38:175-193.
2. Logan, T. M. (2019)"Evaluating urban accessibility: leveraging open-source data and analytics to overcome existing limitations", Environment and Planning Urban Analytics and City Science, 46:897-913.
3. Zhang, Zhehao, Thomas Fisher, and Gang Feng (2012), "Assessing the rationality and walkability of campus layouts", Sustainability, 23: 10116.
4. Holmes, Stephanie, Raymond Huynh, and Adam Millard-Ball, "Pedestrian planning on college campuses", Planning for Higher Education, 2: 65-80.
5. Göçer and Özgür (2019), "Pedestrian tracking in outdoor spaces of a suburban university campus for the investigation of occupancy patterns", Sustainable cities and society, 45: 131-142.
6. Torrens, P. M. (2022), "Data science for pedestrian and high street retailing as a framework for advancing urban informatics to individual scales", Urban informatics, 1:9.